



Supplementary Figure 1: Results of the different analyses conduct using PEM with configuration of cross values. Empty squares are empirical data of extant tetrapods. Filled squares, if present, with brackets, are inferred data of extinct neosuchians. Red indicate an endotherm, blue an ectotherm and grey an unknown condition. Crosses are results of cross validation. Dotted line indicates the limit between endothermy and ectothermy, based on the weaker (for A) are higher (for B and C) known values in our sample of extant endotherms. A) RMR inferences using a model comprising phylogeny and RPOA. B) RBC width inferences using a model comprising phylogeny and canmin. C) RBC area inferences using a model comprising phylogeny and canmin.